

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND CREATIVITY: A CORRELATIONAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The present study examines the relationship between creativity and academic achievement among college students in Assam. Academic achievement is a central concern for educators, parents, policymakers, and society at large, and creativity is increasingly recognized as a factor that can enhance student performance. A sample of 200 college students (100 male and 100 female) from provincialised colleges of Assam was selected using a stratified random sampling technique. Data were analyzed employing the product-moment correlation method. Findings revealed a positive relationship between creativity and academic achievement among the students. As the study addresses a significant and contemporary issue in education, the results hold important implications for students, teachers, parents, academic institutions, and policymakers.

Key Words: Creativity, Academic Achievement, College Students.

Introduction:

Creativity is generally understood as the ability to generate new ideas, forms, or solutions through imaginative skill and innovative thinking. For the present study, creativity is considered as the capacity to invest in new forms of expression and to engage in diverse aspects of thinking, such as divergent thinking, decision-making, innovation, and problem-solving.

As one of the most complex and distinctive characteristics of human behavior, creativity enables individuals to solve problems in novel ways and to produce outcomes that are original, meaningful, and socially valued. It draws upon cognitive processes such as recognition, reasoning, and understanding, and is increasingly viewed as a state of mind that can be developed through learning. Research consistently highlights the association between creativity and student success in academic pursuits, underscoring the responsibility of

educational institutions to nurture creativity as an essential skill for success in all spheres of life.

Academic achievement, on the other hand, refers to the extent of knowledge and skills acquired by students in curricular subjects, usually measured through examinations, marks, or grades. It provides a quantitative assessment of educational attainment and is influenced by multiple factors—creativity being one of the most significant.

Creativity has been described as the foundation of human progress and innovation. Psychological theories emphasize it as one of the highest forms of mental functioning, inherent in every individual. Helson, Agronick, and Roberts (1995) observed that creative individuals are often independent in judgment, assertive, and highly energetic in their work. Sternberg (1991) noted that creativity entails open-mindedness, tolerance of uncertainty, self-motivation, self-confidence, and a willingness to take risks. Similarly, Simonton (1984) defined creativity as the ability to solve problems in new ways and to produce novel, appropriate, and socially valued outcomes. Guilford (1966) further emphasized that “creativity is the key to education in its fullest sense and to the solution of mankind’s most serious problems.”

Against this backdrop, the present study seeks to examine the relationship between creativity and academic achievement among college students in Assam, to understand how creativity influences academic success. Creativity and Academic Achievement:

The development of creativity during student life is not only for the benefit and welfare of the future society but also for the enrichment of finding novel opportunities and insights. The creative thinking abilities enable them to comprehend, respond, and represent their perceptions and understanding of the world. Creativity solves problems and gains mastery. Creativity promotes suitable learning habits. Creativity develops the understanding level of a student.

Creative ability helps the student to develop their skills, attitudes, and knowledge so that their learning and development can benefit. It helps the students to gain and discover new understandings, which lead to sound knowledge and academic excellence.

Nori (2002) studied the sex difference between Creativity and Academic Achievement among high school students. The study revealed that there was no significant relationship between creativity and Academic Achievement, but the result was different for the two sexes. Sebastian Thara (2010) studied Academic Achievement and Creativity. A study found that creativity and Academic Achievement have a significant positive

correlation. Liegies Buno (2014) also studied Creativity and Academic Achievement. This study also found that Creativity and Academic Achievement have a positive correlation.

Objectives:

To study the relationship between Creativity and Academic Achievement of students of class XI

Hypothesis:

There is no significant relationship between Creativity and Academic Achievement of students of class XI

Method:

The investigator adopted a descriptive survey as the method for the present study.

Population and Sample:

The population of the present study consists of many students of class XI studying in various colleges of Assam. In Assam, colleges have XI & XII classes.

As the population of the present study consists of many students belonging to different strata, based on the gender of the students of the college, the investigator adopted a stratified random sampling method.

A sample of 200 students was taken as a sample of the study. The total of 200 respondents includes male, female students.

The sample was collected from 10 colleges affiliated with Gauhati University. From each college, 20 students were selected randomly from class XI, out of which ten are male and ten are female.

Tools Used in the Present Study:

For collecting data, the investigator used the 'Passi-Usha Test of Creative Problem Solving (1996)' to study the creativity of the students.

Academic Achievement Scores were taken from the H.S.L.C.Final examination result of the subject. The mark sheets were collected from the respondent students.

Procedure:

The entire sample of subjects was requested to fill out the creative problem-solving scale. The data so collected was analysed using the correlation technique. To study the significant relationship between creativity and academic achievement of the students, the investigator applied the Product-Moment Correlation technique.

Result Analysis and Findings:**Hypothesis :**

There is no significant relationship between Creativity and Academic achievement of students of class XI.

To test the hypothesis, the investigator has tried to investigate the statistical relationship between the scores of creativity of college students and the academic achievement of the students through employing Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation technique. The correlation value has been presented in Table 1.

Table 1
Correlation between Creativity and Academic Achievement

Variables	Correlation Coefficient	Level of Significance
Creativity and Academic Achievement	0.25	0.01

The result of the relationship, as presented in the above table, reveals that the coefficient of correlation is .25, which indicates a low relationship between the variables. This value is significant even at the 0.01 level. This indicates that there is a significant positive correlation between creativity and the academic achievement of students in class XI. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between creativity and the academic achievement of students of class XI has been rejected. Hence, it can be concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between creativity and the academic achievement of students of class XI.

Discussion and Conclusion

The analysis of the data indicates that there is a positive and significant relationship between creativity and the academic achievement of students at the Class XI level. This finding suggests that higher levels of creativity are associated with better academic performance, thereby reinforcing the importance of fostering creativity in educational contexts.

The results of the present study are consistent with earlier research. Sebastine and Thara (2010) reported that academic achievement can serve as a predictor of creativity, highlighting their interdependence. Similarly, Liegise and Buno (2014) found a positive correlation between creativity and academic achievement among high school students, further supporting the findings of the present study.

However, not all studies align with these results. For instance, Kabanoff (1991) reported no significant relationship between creativity and academic achievement, suggesting that the relationship may vary depending on contextual, cultural, or methodological factors.

Overall, the findings of this study underscore the relevance of creativity as a significant factor influencing academic achievement. Given its implications, educators and policymakers should place greater emphasis on nurturing creativity in students, as it can contribute not only to academic success but also to the holistic development of learners.

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